

STEPS OF LITERACY TEACHING PROCESS. THE PREPARATION PERIOD IN LITERACY TEACHING, TOPICS AND TYPES OF WORK OF READING AND WRITING LESSONS AT THIS STAGE

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'qish ko'nikmasi, so'zni sidirg'a o'qish, bo'g'inlab o'qish, harflab o'qish, yozuv ko'nikmasi, hamma harfni yoza olish, so'zni yozish (bosma yoki yozma), ayrim harflarnigina yozishni bilish (bosma yoki yozma), tovushni analiz qilishga tayyorgarlik ko'nikmasi ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Sidirg'a o'qish, yozuv ko'nikmasi, analiz, sintez, grammatika, imlo, leksikologiya.

Аннотация: В этой статье раскрываются навыки чтения, чтение слова вслух, чтение по слогам, чтение по буквам, навыки письма, умение писать всю букву, умение писать слово (печатное или письменное), умение писать только отдельные буквы (печатное или письменное), навыки подготовки к звуковому анализу.

Ключевые слова: Чтение, навыки письма, анализ, синтез, грамматика, орфография, лексикология.

Annotation: This article reveals the reading skills, the ability to read a word, read a syllable, read a letter, the writing skills, the ability to write all letters, write a

word (printed or written), the ability to write only certain letters (printed or written), the ability to prepare for sound analysis.

Keywords: Mindfulness reading, writing skills, analysis, synthesis, grammar, spelling, lexicology.

Literacy training consists of three periods:

1. Preparation period.
2. Alphabet letter period.
3. After the alphabet - the period of teaching to read and write.

The preparatory period lasts a week, the importance of this period is that children should learn to develop speech and write letters. The tasks of the preparatory period are as follows:

1. School life is introduced, rules and requirements are taught.
2. The teacher organizes a team of students and inculcates in their minds that each student is a member of this team.
3. It is explained how to sit properly at the desk, raise your hand before answering a question or answer, speak slowly so that everyone can hear, keep books and notebooks in order, take good care of school equipment, etc.
4. The teacher gets to know the students and studies them.
5. Pupils are introduced to educational tools. First of all, the book "Alifbe" will be introduced. Its cover, author, pages are introduced.
6. How to keep a notebook is explained.

7. In order to develop students' speech, they work on words, sentences, and stories.

8. It is taught to analyze the sound.

Analytical exercises are mainly used to teach students to analyze speech. In this, the students perform the initial exercises on dividing the sentence into words.

They are:

1. Sentences are made based on the pictures in the alphabet book.
2. Determine how many words are in each sentence.
3. The words in the structured sentence are marked with lines.
4. Sentences are put into the scheme.
5. Words are divided into syllables: lo-la, gul-don.
6. Information is given about some vowels and consonants in the word.

Teaching writing:

It is a difficult and important activity for first-graders to write letters and letters correctly. In the pre-alphabetic period, children perform exercises that prepare them for writing.

First of all, it is necessary to teach children to sit properly and freely, to hold the pen correctly, and to place the notebook on the desk at a normal angle during the writing exercise. For this, a picture called "Sit straight when writing" is used. They are introduced to the lines of the notebook and are taught to write parts of letters on it and to correctly measure their spacing.

In the initial period of literacy training, educational activities are organized

taking into account the age characteristics of a seven-year-old child and his attention. During this period, students cannot do the same work for a long time. Therefore, the type of work should be changed every 10-15 minutes. Work in the lesson should be organized in this way: storytelling and conversations are alternated with active movement of students and physical exercises.

After the conversation about dividing the sentence into words based on the content of the pictures from the alphabet, a fairy tale is told to the students. They draw pictures of the heroes of this fairy tale. One sentence is taken from a fairy tale, it is asked how many words are in the sentence, and the diagram is drawn on the board with a straight line. The students themselves do such exercises on the board and in their notebooks.

In the writing class, the teacher's explanation is alternated with the students' finger movement exercises, that is, the students show how the fingers of the hand holding the pen are raised and lowered. Pupils write, if their hands get tired, exercises are performed to move their hands and fingers.

From the point of view of organizing the educational process, students should be differentiated and individualized in the process of literacy. This is due to significant differences in the general development of children. The level of reading and writing readiness of seven-year-old children entering the 1st grade, according to research, has shown that they know 80% of the letters or all the letters.

Most of them read analytically - syllables, some synthetically, that is, they read with words. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the teacher, from the point of

view of teaching perspectives, to systematically introduce the propaedeutic elements of grammar, word formation, spelling, lexicology, from the psychological and linguistic point of view, taking into account the accessibility and convenience of learning sounds and letters. Looking for a rational order, on the other hand, the tasks of providing education and development are assigned.

The process of writing with a first grader is divided into many independent actions. In this case, the student should hold the pencil correctly and place the notebook at the required level. Having learned to write a letter, the student should remember its shape and elements, put a line in the notebook taking into account the ruler, remember how the pen moves along the line. If he writes a whole word, he must also remember how one letter connects to another and calculate that the word fits into a line. He should remember how to sit without moving the hole of the notebook. The child is not yet used to performing these tasks, so all the above actions require conscious actions. This not only speeds up writing, but also makes the child mentally and physically tired. When a first-grader writes, his whole body, especially the muscles of the hands and wrists, get tired. This indicates the need for special physical exercises during classes.

The teacher observes how the student writes. The pen slowly, vaguely moves to the paper, flickers; After the student writes, the teacher checks it, compares it with the model, and sometimes corrects it. The movements of the hands are often accompanied by movements of the head or tongue.

By checking the student's notebooks, the teacher makes sure that the same

letters are written differently in different situations. This is the result of lack of skill, fatigue. For students, rewriting letters and words is not a mechanical process, but a conscious activity. The student puts a lot of effort into his work.

A special study of the level of children's speech preparation is required for the proper organization of literacy learning. Such special learning begins before the child comes to school, that is, in August, or even before. In the spring, the teacher visits the families of first-graders and kindergartens. He talks with them, asks questions, recommends to tell a story about something, determines the general knowledge level of children. Taking into account the collected data, speech preparation is recorded. This is necessary for an individual or differential approach to the child in education.

To take into account the result of dating and study speech preparation, the following table can be recommended:

I. Reading skills:

1. He reads the word by heart.
2. He reads in syllables.
3. Reads by letter (incorrect reading skill).
4. He knows a few letters, but does not read.
5. He knows only some letters.

II. Writing skills:

1. Everyone knows how to write a letter, writes a word (printed or written).
2. He knows how to write only certain letters (printed or written).

3. Does not know how to write at all.

III. Preparatory skills for sound analysis.

1. The word is divided into syllables.
2. Separates the sound in a word or syllable.
3. All pronounce the sound correctly.
4. He pronounces some sounds incorrectly.

IV. Reciting the poem from memory.

1. He knows three poems and recites them with pleasure.
2. He knows a couple of poems. He is ashamed to say.
3. He does not know how to recite a single poem by heart.

V. Verbal connected speech. Telling a story.

1. He knows how to tell one or more fairy tales.
2. He tries to tell a story, but he cannot.
3. He doesn't know how to tell a story, he doesn't even try to learn.

VI. Verbal connection speech, expression of opinion.

(Tell me what you see in the picture.)

1. A connected story of more than 20 words, several sentences.
2. From 10 to 20 words, several sentences.
3. 10 word, connected answer.
4. A short sentence of 3-4 words.

Russian pedagogue Ushinsky called his method "writing and reading method". He convincingly proved that writing cannot be separated from reading.

He believed that writing based on voice analysis should be started before reading. According to Ushinsky's "Alphabet", children are first introduced to handwriting, and then printed letters are introduced. But still, a new letter is first given in writing after studying the sound.

K. D. Ushinsky combined analysis and synthesis in his methodology, introduced a system of analytical and synthetic exercises using sounds, syllables and words. In his system, analysis and synthesis are inseparable and support each other.

The advantage of his methodology was that he relied on live speech. Literacy is related to the development of students' speech. From the first lessons, children work with folk proverbs and riddles; readable texts are available for children. Sentences and words taken from students' speech are used for voice analysis.

Ushinsky considered his developmental nature to be the advantage of the methodology, and indeed, analytical and synthetic exercises, constant attention to the development of speech, attention to reading information, conversations, the relationship between writing and reading - all this created a consistent system of developing mental abilities of students. Sound analytical-synthetic method thus represents a big step in the struggle for public education. This literally destroys the dogmatism of the method.

Ushinsky's entire pedagogical system was aimed at the comprehensive development of the child, the development of his thinking and speech, and the literacy method he developed was the first link in his system.

In conclusion, we can say that from the point of view of organizing the educational process, students should be differentiated and individualized in the process of literacy. We can say that this is related to significant differences in the general development of children.

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